

Understanding Vulnerable Road Users Awareness Messages generation dynamics: the case of e-bikes

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Abstract—Electric bikes (e-bikes) are one of the major development assets towards green and inclusive urban transportation. Their high speed, up to 25 km/h, comparable to that of small motorcycles and pedelecs, make e-bikes more prone to traffic accidents than conventional bicycles. Hence, it is crucial to enhance the safety of these Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) through Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications, providing connectivity among road entities. The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has specified awareness messages, carrying position and kinematics information, to extend the horizon of vehicles and VRUs. While the generation patterns and relevant performance of such messages have been extensively investigated in the literature when considering vehicles, a few works have analyzed the so-called VRU Awareness Messages (VAMs) transmitted by VRUs, and to the best of our knowledge, none when considering e-bikes. In this work, we focus on e-bikes and, collecting mobility traces of participants with different riding skills in the city of Karlsruhe, Germany, we assess the dynamics of VAMs generated according to ETSI rules and additional triggers suggested by the Fifth Generation Automotive Association (5GAA). The built prototype collects mobility data from the e-bike as well as other context information, thus providing helpful insights about VAM generation patterns and their impact on the network load. Results show a low channel load for all the considered trigger conditions, satisfying the ETSI load constraints.

Index Terms—Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X), Vulnerable Road User (VRU), e-bike, Cooperative Automated Driving (CAD), VAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Union (EU) and United Nations (UN) are struggling to make mobility safer, with the target to halve the number of road deaths by 2030. Based on available data for 2021 across the EU, 52% of road traffic fatalities occurred on rural roads, versus 39% in urban areas and 9% on motorways. In particular, in urban areas, Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) (i.e., pedestrians, cyclists and users of powered two-wheelers) represent just under 70% of total fatalities [1].

A serious cause for concern is the trend in the number of cyclists killed on EU roads, where cycling is particularly widespread. While vehicles are constantly increasing the occupants' protection, the same fatalities decrease trend does not apply to VRUs, that being unprotected by an outside shield, are more prone to a high risk of injury in the event of a collision with a vehicle.

Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications, through which vehicles and other road entities can improve the awareness of their surroundings, even under hostile conditions and well beyond their own perception, can contribute to make roads safer also for non-vehicle occupants [2].

The Car-to-Car Communication Consortium (C2C-CC) conceived a V2X deployment roadmap organized in subsequent phases named Day 1, Day 2, etc., indicating the transition from phases in which the V2X technology is used for dissemination of local status information towards phases where V2X communications become crucial to enable Cooperative Automated Driving (CAD) [3].

Unlike previous deployment phases where VRUs are passively detected by vehicles, in the Day 3+ phase, VRUs are expected to be able to explicitly announce their presence, by transmitting VRU Awareness Messages (VAMs) [4] through V2X communications. Similarly to the so-called Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) [5] transmitted by vehicles, VAMs allow VRUs to broadcast their position and speed information to vehicles and other VRUs in proximity.

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has specified packet formats and kinematically-driven generation rules for both CAMs and VAMs. A vehicle/VRU compares its current kinematic measurements with the ones advertised into the last transmitted message and, if the difference between them is above pre-defined thresholds, a new message transmission is triggered. More messages are transmitted when the kinematics parameters vary more quickly and, hence, the behaviour of the transmitter is less predictable.

In the past recent years a plenty of works have extensively analyzed the CAM generation dynamics and the relevant network performance, e.g., [6], [7], [8], just to name a few. Only recently, the raised awareness about the impelling need to target the protection of VRUs has fostered the interest in studying VAMs, e.g., [2], [9], [10], [11].

Belonging to the VRUs landscape, electric bikes (e-bikes) are gaining momentum as one of the most common micro-mobility option contributing to a more sustainable and inclusive transportation. As e-bike usage continues to rise, it becomes increasingly important to understand their unique dynamics, differences to traditional bicycles, safety considerations, and

interactions within the broader transportation infrastructure [12], [13]. Research focusing on e-bikes already sheds light on their distinct characteristics, including their potential to extend cycling distances, appeal to a diverse range of users, and influence urban as well as sub-urban and rural mobility patterns [14]–[19].

However, conventional definitions of VRUs lack to differentiate between traditional bicycles and e-bikes or pedelecs with a maximum assisted speed of 25km/h or 32km/h [12], [13], [20]–[22]. The literature mainly focuses on VAMs generated by bicycles [9], [23], [24]. However, relevant findings may not hold when considering e-bikes, due to their different dynamics [15], potential differences in cycling behavior [25], increased bicycle weight and higher average cycled speeds [19], compared to conventional bikes. Hence, the VAM generation patterns from e-bikes entail a proper understanding.

Moreover, e-bikes, as e-scooters, are the only VRUs that, theoretically, can automatically slow down when at risk, regardless of the human’s status/attention. Hence, including them in the CAD landscape could provide tangible benefits over the short term.

Granted these motivations, this work aims to provide the following main original contributions:

- We build a prototype to retrieve e-bike parameters (e.g., speed, cadence, position and timestamp) as well as cyclist information (e.g., her stability).
- We collect realistic datasets involving several e-bike cyclists with different skills moving in the city of Karlsruhe, Germany.
- We analyze the generation patterns of VAMs by the e-bike cyclists, according to the ETSI rules and derive possible extensions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the ETSI specifications concerning the generation of VAMs by VRUs and scans the recent relevant literature. Section III presents the conducted study as well as the related results. Concluding remarks and hints on future works are provided in Section IV.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATIONS

A. The ETSI specifications

ETSI specified the VRU Basic Service (VBS) [12] with the aim to improve road safety by focusing on VRUs. Specifically, a VRU can be a pedestrian, a road worker, an animal, a skater, a cyclist, a motorcycle driver, etc.

These road users belong to a specific VRU profile based on their features, as specified in [4]. These features are average and maximum speed, minimum and average communication range, environment (i.e., the physical place where the VRU exists), average weight and standard deviation, trajectory ambiguity (i.e., the reliability level of VRU trajectory predictions), and cluster size. The profiles specified in [4] are four:

- Profile 1 includes road users not using mechanical devices for their journeys (e.g., pedestrians, prams, bikers off their bikes).

- Profile 2 contains riders of light vehicles, eventually electrically powered (e.g., bikers, skaters, e-scooters, wheelchair users) and with a maximum speed lower than 25 km/h.
- Profile 3 comprises users of two-wheel motorized vehicles driving on the road (e.g., motorcyclists, side-cars). Note that this profile includes drivers and passengers.
- Profile 4 incorporates animals representing a safety risk for road users during their trips (e.g., dogs, cats, horses, and wild animals in rural scenarios). Most of this profile members are detected indirectly.

Furthermore, ETSI specifications conceive the cluster concept, i.e., the creation of a group of VRUs with similar kinematic features (e.g., speed, heading), where the communication burden relies on the Cluster Leader (CL) only, in order to reduce the channel load as well as the battery consumption of the cluster members [4], [12].

Similarly to other ETSI Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) messages, VAMs are generated based on different thresholds. The first threshold regards time constraints: an ITS Station (i.e., a VRU in this case) must start a new VAM generation event at least every T_{GenVam} , namely a time period belonging to a window ranging from 100 ms (i.e., $T_{GenVamMin}$) to 5000 ms (i.e., $T_{GenVamMax}$). The triggers related to VAM generation must be checked periodically, with period $T_{CheckVamGen}$ which should be equal or lower than $T_{GenVamMin}$ (e.g., 100 ms).

Specifically, a new VAM must be generated by a VRU if:

- The last VAM has been generated more than 5000 ms ago.
- The VRU position has changed more than 4 meters, compared to the last shared VAM.
- The VRU changed its heading more than 4° , contrasted with the last VAM.
- The VRU altered its speed more than 0.5 m/s since the last shared VAM.
- The VRU will intercept another road user’s trajectory with a probability higher than a certain threshold.
- The VRU chooses to join a cluster.
- The VRU and another road user are too close.

Once one of the previous trigger conditions is verified, the VRU generates a VAM according to the format specified in [12]. Specifically, this format foresees the presence of mandatory and optional elements (i.e., containers), as illustrated in Fig. 1.

The mandatory containers are the *ITS Packet Data Unit (PDU) Header* (i.e., an element common to each ETSI ITS message type and describing the ITS and the message identifiers), the *Generation Delta Time* (i.e., a container indicating the VAM generation instant), the *Basic Container* (i.e., an element describing the VRU type and its last position), the *High-Frequency Container* (i.e., the element describing VRU heading, speed, acceleration, and other VRU fast changing attributes), and the *Low-Frequency Container* (i.e., a container describing VRU slow changing data, such as size and profile).

The optional containers are the *Cluster Information Container* (employed when clustering is enabled to describe cluster identifier, bounding boxes, and involved VRU profiles), the *Cluster Operation Container* (employed to handle cluster breakup, joining, or living phases), and the *Motion Prediction Container* (describing VRU past and future trajectories).

Fig. 1: VAM structure.

B. Literature overview

Recent studies about VAM generations have been carried out to analyze message generation patterns compliant with ETSI rules [2], [9], custom solutions to modify these patterns [9], [24] and approaches leveraging VRU clustering [10], [11]. All these solutions aim to improve VRUs’ safety level, avoiding network resource wasting and additionally to reduce the battery usage of mobile devices transmitting VAMs.

The work in [2] compares different VRUs protection mechanisms, from passive approaches based on sensor-based detection only to active approaches that foresee the exchange of VAMs. Despite showing inherent benefits when exchanging VAMs, the study does not analyze the ETSI message generation rules in detail. This is instead what is done in [9], through real datasets acquired while riding a bike and an e-scooter around the City of Bologna. The obtained results show that the actual ETSI generation rules produce a huge channel load compared to the proposed customized heading triggering solution due to the amount of unnecessary shared VAMs (i.e., a message reporting slightly different data compared to the previous one). Also, the custom solution maintains an acceptable VAM sharing rate in terms of traveled meters, by preserving safety.

The study in [24] leverages a Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) server to analyse and extract valuable information about the neighborhood from the received CAMs/VAMs and adapts their transmission frequency accordingly.

Similarly, the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) recognizes the need to consider additional information for the VBS management. In particular, in [13] the 5GAA describes some additional fields that should be included in the actual ETSI VAM and Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) Personal Safety Messages (PSM) implementations to describe deeply VRU features. Specifically, these fields are closely related to the cyclist VRU profile (i.e., Profile 2, according to Section

II-A) and should be used to represent information such as cyclist stability and reaction time, environmental conditions, and future paths. These new fields allow the smart mobility system to focus on poor skills (and potentially more exposed to road risks) VRUs.

C. Contributions

From the analysis of the literature it clearly emerges that VAM generation dynamics need to be carefully analyzed and triggering rules and relevant thresholds properly adapted to the VRU profiles and to road environments.

To complement the existing state of the art and filling the identified gaps, this work will consider realistic mobility traces from e-bikes collected through a purpose-built prototype which allows to collect kinematics information as provided by the Global Positioning System (GPS) as well as additional context parameters. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to consider e-bikes as VRUs.

Specifically, we aim to analyze the behaviour of e-bike cyclists with different skills and the impact of this on the ETSI VAM generation patterns. Moreover, the case for additional information to be carried out in VAMs to capture the cyclist stability, in agreement with 5GAA suggestions, is examined, to unveil cyclist skills.

III. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. The prototype

To collect mobility traces, we leverage a size M and L (according to the height of participants) *HNF Nicolai UD4 All-Terrain 27.5"* e-bike utilizing the *4th Generation Bosch Smart System Performance Line CX* motor, as used in [26] for cycling experience assessment, equipped with a maximum torque of 85 Nm. The e-bike is compliant with German traffic regulations, specifically §63a(2) of StVZO, ensuring its secure operation in regular traffic while providing motor assistance up to 25 km/h. To ensure traffic regulation compliance, e-bikes typically measure speed using a magnet attached to the wheel spoke. As the magnet passes a sensor mounted on the frame, the current speed is computed using the known wheel circumference and the time elapsed since the last trigger. Once the e-bike reaches the speed limit, the motor turns off. Similarly, adding a magnet on the pedal allows for the measurement of cadence in Revolutions per Minute (RPM) by tracking the time of each rotation.

A microcontroller embedded in the e-bike (see Fig. 2(a)) and equipped with Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) monitors the current speed and cadence. It records these measurements, along with the motor assistance state (i.e., *on* or *off*), adjusted speed limit and current geographic position as retrieved through a GPS module as well as timestamp, onto a SD memory card. The prototype also retrieves information from the accelerometer and gyroscope module connected to the Arduino board. The entire system is powered by a dedicated battery, ensuring a stable supply of 12.0 V for reliable operation. Table I reports the main hardware components of the developed prototype.

(a) Prototype.

(b) Map.

Fig. 2: Developed prototype (a) and identified trip over the map (b).

B. Field tests

The cycling study took place in the city of Karlsruhe for a 1.1km-long trip, as illustrated in Figure 2(b), on flat terrain, in autumn 2023. A total of 15 participants (13 male, 2 female) aged from 23 to 40 years (average = 27.7 years, standard deviation = 4.7) has been involved. On average, the participants had a height of 1.80 m (standard deviation = 0.11 m) and a weight of 80 kg (standard deviation = 18.5 kg). Participants

TABLE I: Prototype hardware components.

Component type	Component name
Main microcontroller	Arduino Uno Wi-Fi Rev. 2
GPS module	U-BLOX NEO-7M
Memory Shield	Data Logger Module Shield
Accelerometer	GY-LSM6DS3 module
Gyroscope	GY-LSM6DS3 module

were recruited through university mailing lists and WhatsApp groups. Studies were only conducted during daytime.

C. Results

1) *Speed profiles*: Results are reported for two different participants representative of an experienced cyclist and an inexperienced one. This classification is based on a preliminary questionnaire filled out by each participant. Specifically, the survey asks about the perceived average speed during trips, the number of rides and kilometers covered per week, and the type of bike usually employed. So, the experienced cyclist reports higher values to the aforementioned questions compared to the inexperienced one. Speed traces, collected as described in Section III-A, are reported for the two participants in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). It can be reasonably observed that the experienced cyclist rides the e-bike while maintaining a speed that is very close to the speed limit (25 km/h) and in some cases, the participant oversteps it without motor support, while the inexperienced cyclist even after a preliminary phase of understanding and testing the e-bike never reaches the speed limit.

2) *ETSI VAM generation triggers*: Starting from the traces collected through the Arduino-based prototype, similarly to [9], VAM traces have been generated through a custom Python script that resembles the ETSI generation rules for VRU profile 2. The VAM trace corresponding to the experienced cyclist is reported in Fig. 4. It can be observed that the VAM generation period T_{GenVam} is always below $T_{GenVamMax}$. The minimum registered value of T_{GenVam} coincides with $T_{CheckVamGen}$ (set to 100 ms), although it exhibits a few occurrences. Overall, the trend is quite irregular.

Specifically, during the same trip 140 VAMs are generated for the experienced participant, whereas they are 151 VAMs for the inexperienced one. Also, for the former the average T_{GenVam} is equal to 1427.88 ms, while for the latter is 1686.67 ms.

Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) report the percentages of VAMs triggered by different conditions for each participant: position change labeled as *Distance*, heading change labeled as *Heading*, speed change labeled as *Speed* and the case in which more than one triggering condition is met, labeled as *Mixed*.

It can be observed that for both kinds of participants, the VAM generation is mainly triggered by variations in the position. VAMs triggered by speed variations are larger for the experienced cyclist, for which instead the portion of triggers due to heading is less significant. This confirms the intuition that the cycling of the experienced participant is more stable, although moving at higher pace.

VAMs are all generated before the expiration of the 5s-long timeout, hence no triggers due to such events are reported.

Still, results show that the percentage of heading-triggered VAMs is not as significant as expected. This trend has to be ascribed to the quality of the leveraged GPS device and of its signal over the considered route, covering both a urban area and tree shading environments.

3) *Additional VAM generation triggers*: The built prototype allows to collect additional information concerning the stability of the e-bike as captured through the embedded gyroscope. This data could complement potential failure of the GPS-provided heading data, which consequently may not trigger VAMs under some circumstances, and allow to capture the stability of the e-bike cyclist, in agreement with what suggested by 5GAA. Collecting such data could have a twofold aim: (i) to trigger additional VAMs and prevent accidents in potentially dangerous conditions, e.g., in the cyclist longitudinal scenario, where a vehicle and a cyclist both travel in the same direction on the road, likely very close to each other [27], but also in case of sudden turning, and (ii) to track the cyclist behaviour and suggest, accordingly, a dynamic adaptation of the trigger thresholds and, consequently, of the VAM generation rate. Overall, this could contribute to improve the safety of VRUs.

Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b) report, respectively, the VAM triggers distribution when considering an additional triggering condition for the experienced and inexperienced e-bike cyclists: the VRU altered its stability (Δ_g) more than 4° since the last shared VAM.

The variation in the stability triggers almost of all the VAMs (about the 81.6% for the experienced cyclist and 83.9% for the inexperienced one, as depicted in Fig. 6), with a T_{GenVam} equal to 338.24 ms for the experienced cyclist and 340.84 ms for the inexperienced participant, significantly lower than in the previous case with only ETSI triggers (respectively, 1427.88 ms and 1686.67 ms).

Table II compares the average T_{GenVam} , the percentage of triggers due to heading as per ETSI specifications and due to stability variations as captured by the gyroscope and the corresponding overall number of generated packets. Different thresholds have been considered similarly to what done in [9]. Results clearly show that the number of generated VAMs and the VAM generation interval are quite sensitive to the setting of the threshold.

The lower the threshold, the higher the generation frequency of VAMs. This could be an issue if the higher channel load corresponds to VAMs reporting slightly different information compared to the one triggered by ETSI legacy thresholds. Indeed, minimizing the amount of exchanged messages while maximizing their informativeness is crucial for deploying VRU Awareness Services in densely populated scenarios (i.e., urban scenarios), where radio resources should be shared by vehicles and VRUs.

To understand the impact on channel load we measure the *duty cycle* defined by ETSI [28] as the ratio, expressed as a percentage of the transmitter total “on” time on one carrier frequency, relative to 1s-long period. According to ETSI specifications, it should be equal or lower than 3%, meaning that a station can occupy at most 3%, i.e., 30 ms, of channel time within 1 s. As reported in Table II, interestingly, the duty cycle is very low and well beyond the ETSI limit, even when the gyroscope-trigger is added.

Moreover, in terms of exchanged bytes, conveying the sta-

bility value incurs only additional 6 bytes in the VAM legacy format carrying the high-frequency container only. According to the average T_{GenVam} for experienced and inexperienced cyclists and considering an average VAM packet size of 89 bytes (i.e., a realistic value reported in [29]), the average per-bike-throughput is negligible and nearly equal to 2.3 kbps.

It is also worth remarking that, unlike for pedestrians, the higher generation frequency of VAMs is expected to not be a big concern in terms of energy consumption for the e-bike.

(a) Experienced e-bike cyclist (average speed = 18.68 km/h).

(b) Inexperienced e-bike cyclist (average speed = 15.06 km/h).

Fig. 3: Speed trace.

Fig. 4: VAM trace of the experienced cyclist, with ETSI triggers.

(a) Experienced e-bike cyclist.

(b) Inexperienced e-bike cyclist.

Fig. 5: Distribution of ETSI triggers for the generated VAMs.

TABLE II: VAMs metrics for the experienced cyclist.

Parameter	ETSI only	ETSI+ $\Delta_g=4^\circ$	ETSI+ $\Delta_g=7^\circ$	ETSI+ $\Delta_g=10^\circ$
T_GenVam [ms]	1427.88	338.24	546.18	743.13
Heading trigger [%]	15.7	1.9	2.7	5.2
Gyroscope trigger [%]	-	81.6	68.6	55.4
Duty cycle [%]	0.07	0.3	0.18	0.13
Total generated VAMs	140	591	366	269

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work we have investigated the VAM generation patterns for e-bikes. Field tests have been performed by involving different e-bike cyclists to collect mobility traces, along with kinematics and context parameters.

A study of the VAM triggers (and relevant thresholds), as foreseen in ETSI specifications, has been performed by considering participants with different cycling behaviours.

The possibility of considering an additional trigger, complementing the GPS-provided heading, to account for the stability of the e-bike cyclist has been analyzed and the relevant VAMs load evaluated.

(a) Experienced e-bike cyclist.

(b) Inexperienced e-bike cyclist.

Fig. 6: Distribution of triggers for the generated VAMs also including the gyrosopic value variations $(x,y) > 4^\circ$.

By considering variations in stability as a supplementary condition for VAM generation we aim to enhance the detection of hazardous situations, especially in situations with poor GPS signals, and enable dynamic adjustments to trigger thresholds, thereby optimizing safety measures for cyclists. The proposal is shown not to determine a huge channel load, while satisfying the ETSI load constraints.

All in all, achieved results point out the need to further assess the VAMs dynamics for e-bikes in more complex scenarios. For example, the latter ones could include several e-bikes, e-bikes and vehicles (e.g., cars, trucks, buses, etc.) and more challenging road characteristics (e.g., climbs, sharp turns, etc.)

in order to produce a more unstable trip, and so on.

Future works will unveil the delivery performance of VAMs exchanged through the Cellular V2X technology, either over Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) or Vehicle-to-Network (V2N) links.

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REFERENCES

- [1] “Road safety in the EU: fatalities below pre-pandemic levels but progress remains too slow,” 2023, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/road-safety-eu-fatalities-below-pre-pandemic-levels-progress-remains-too-slow-2023-02-21_en [Accessed: 12 February 2024].
- [2] S. Lobo, A. Festag, and C. Facchi, “Enhancing the Safety of Vulnerable Road Users: Messaging Protocols for V2X Communication,” in *2022 IEEE 96th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2022-Fall)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–7.
- [3] CAR 2 CAR Communication Consortium, “Guidance for Day 2 and beyond roadmap,” 2019, https://www.car-2-car.org/fileadmin/documents/General_Documents/C2CCC_WP_2072_RoadmapDay2AndBeyond.pdf [Accessed: 12 February 2024].
- [4] “ETSI TS 103 300-2 v2.1.1. Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) awareness; Part 2: Functional Architecture and Requirements definition,” May 2020.
- [5] “ETSI EN 302 637-2 v1.3.1 Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Part 2: Specification of Cooperative Awareness Basic Service.”
- [6] N. Lyamin, A. Vinel, M. Jonsson, and B. Bellalta, “Cooperative awareness in VANETs: On ETSI EN 302 637-2 performance,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 17–28, 2017.
- [7] J. Santa, F. Pereñíguez, A. Moragón, and A. F. Skarmeta, “Experimental evaluation of CAM and DENM messaging services in vehicular communications,” *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 46, pp. 98–120, 2014.
- [8] R. Molina-Masegosa, M. Sepulcre, J. Gozalvez, F. Berens, and V. Martínez, “Empirical models for the realistic generation of cooperative awareness messages in vehicular networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 5713–5717, 2020.
- [9] L. Lusvarghi, C. A. Grazia, M. Klápez, M. Casoni, and M. L. Merani, “Awareness Messages by Vulnerable Road Users and Vehicles: Field Tests Via LTE-V2X,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, 2023.
- [10] S. Lobo, L. B. da Silva, and C. Facchi, “To cluster or not to cluster: A VRU clustering based on V2X communication,” in *IEEE ITSC*, 2023.
- [11] M. Rupp and L. Wischhof, “Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Vulnerable Road User Clustering in C-V2X Systems,” in *2023 IEEE International Conference on Omni-layer Intelligent Systems (COINS)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [12] “ETSI TS 103 300-3 v2.2.1. Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) awareness; Part 3: Specification of VRU awareness basic service,” February 2023.
- [13] “5GAA; Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) Protection,” August 2020.
- [14] M. S. Hasnine, A. Dianat, and K. N. Habib, “Investigating the factors affecting the distance travel and health conditions of e-bike users in Toronto,” *Transportation research interdisciplinary perspectives*, vol. 8, p. 100265, 2020.
- [15] P. A. Plazier, G. Weitkamp, and A. E. van den Berg, ““Cycling was never so easy!” An analysis of e-bike commuters’ motives, travel behaviour and experiences using GPS-tracking and interviews,” *Journal of transport geography*, vol. 65, pp. 25–34, 2017.
- [16] Q. Sun, T. Feng, A. Kemperman, and A. Spahn, “Modal shift implications of e-bike use in the Netherlands: Moving towards sustainability?” *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 78, p. 102202, 2020.
- [17] A. B. Jahre, E. Bere, S. Nordengen, A. Solbraa, L. B. Andersen, A. Riiser, and H. B. Bjørnarå, “Public employees in South-Western Norway using an e-bike or a regular bike for commuting—A cross-sectional comparison on sociodemographic factors, commuting frequency and commuting distance,” *Preventive medicine reports*, vol. 14, p. 100881, 2019.
- [18] P. Rérat, “The rise of the e-bike: Towards an extension of the practice of cycling?” *Mobilities*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 423–439, 2021.
- [19] K. Schleinitz, T. Petzoldt, L. Franke-Bartholdt, J. Krems, and T. Gehlert, “The german naturalistic cycling study—comparing cycling speed of riders of different e-bikes and conventional bicycles,” *Safety Science*, vol. 92, pp. 290–297, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925753515001976>
- [20] E. Fishman and C. Chery, “E-bikes in the mainstream: Reviewing a decade of research,” *Transport reviews*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 72–91, 2016.
- [21] A. Avenoso and J. Beckmann, “The safety of vulnerable road users in the Southern, Eastern and Central European Countries (The “SEC belt”),” *Brussels: European Transport Safety Council*, 2005.
- [22] L. Reish, “Comparing Demographic Trends in Vulnerable Road User Fatalities and the US Population, 1980-2019,” *Research Note. Report No. DOT HS*, vol. 813, p. 178, 2021.
- [23] T. Lara, A. Yáñez, S. Céspedes, and A. S. Hafid, “Impact of safety message generation rules on the awareness of vulnerable road users,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 10, p. 3375, 2021.
- [24] C. Zoghalmi, R. Kacimi, and R. Dhaou, “Dynamics of cooperative and vulnerable awareness messages in V2X safety applications,” in *2022 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing (IWCMC)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 853–858.
- [25] P. Huertas-Leyva, M. Dozza, and N. Baldanzini, “Investigating cycling kinematics and braking maneuvers in the real world: e-bikes make cyclists move faster, brake harder, and experience new conflicts,” *Transportation research part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, vol. 54, pp. 211–222, 2018.
- [26] A. Laqua, J. Schnee, J. Pletinckx, and M. Meywerk, “Exploring User Experience in Sustainable Transport with Explainable AI Methods Applied to E-Bikes,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 20, p. 11277, 2023.
- [27] F. Char and T. Serre, “Analysis of pre-crash characteristics of passenger car to cyclist accidents for the development of advanced drivers assistance systems,” *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, vol. 136, p. 105408, 2020.
- [28] “ETSI EN 302 663 v1.3.0. Intelligent Transport System (ITS); ITS-G5 Access layer specification for Intelligent Transport Systems operating in the 5 GHz frequency band,” October 2019.
- [29] D. Maksimovski and C. Facchi, “Decentralized V2X maneuver sharing and coordination message for cooperative driving: Analysis in mixed traffic,” in *2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 5182–5189.